

Enhancing research integrity with ORCID data

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Purpose

In today's global and interconnected research environment, the need for transparency, integrity, and trust in scientific contributions is central. ORCID's infrastructure addresses these critical needs by providing persistent identifiers (PIDs) for people and connections to their contributions, affiliations and activities, which serve as foundational tools to support research integrity (Haak et al., 2012). Rather than focusing solely on the challenges of verifying researcher identities in a complex and international landscape, ORCID promotes the concept of identity demonstration. This allows researchers to build their identity over time by leveraging trusted data from multiple sources, such as affiliations, grants, research production, and peer review activities. The cumulative process of identity demonstration provides a verifiable timeline of a researcher's career, improving the visibility and trustworthiness of their contributions (ORCID, 2024).

In parallel, ORCID supports Open Science practices by adhering to the FAIR data principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) (Sadler, 2022). These principles aim to make research outputs more discoverable, accessible, and reusable by the global scientific community (Wilkinson et al., 2016). By aligning its infrastructure with these principles, ORCID enhances the transparency and reproducibility of scholarly research.

Results

ORCID's infrastructure provides tangible benefits for the research ecosystem, mainly through its use of PIDs. These PIDs act as building blocks within the research ecosystem, connecting various entities such as researchers, institutions, funders, and research outputs. The interoperable nature of ORCID's infrastructure allows these connections to be standardised and maintained across platforms, enabling more efficient discovery and collaboration (Lin & Strasser, 2021).

One of ORCID's key contributions is its inclusion of provenance metadata for each item in a researcher's ORCID record. This metadata provides a transparent record of where the data originated, whether manually added by the researcher or validated through an institutional integration. By including provenance details, ORCID strengthens confidence in the data's trustworthiness, allowing the research community to trace information back to its original sources (ORCID, 2019).

ORCID's trust program is another fundamental element that ensures the integrity of records. Built on individual control, reliability, accountability, and integrity principles, this program establishes a robust system for maintaining accurate and trustworthy information (ORCID, 2019). Researchers retain control over their ORCID records while authenticated workflows, community monitoring, and institutional integrations ensure that records are continuously

validated. Member organisations, for example, can securely add data to researcher profiles through authenticated APIs, ensuring the information is sourced from trusted and verified entities (ORCID, 2019).

Furthermore, the trustworthiness of ORCID records evolves over time as more validated data is contributed. This ongoing validation process builds a progressively reliable and credible record of a researcher's career. Even manually added data is subject to community oversight, with mechanisms in place to address disputes and resolve inaccuracies. The combination of institutional verification and community-driven accountability creates a research ecosystem built on a foundation of trust.

Value

ORCID is pivotal in the current research landscape by enhancing scholarly work's transparency, discoverability, and reproducibility. By supporting Open Science practices, ORCID ensures that research is more accessible and shareable across disciplines and borders. This is essential for fostering a collaborative research environment where data can be securely shared and knowledge can be built upon.

Integrating FAIR data principles into ORCID's infrastructure is of significant value to the research community. It accelerates the discovery of knowledge, improves the accessibility of research outputs, and facilitates the reuse of data in a standardised manner. These principles are critical to ensuring that research data can be leveraged effectively by current researchers and future generations.

Additionally, ORCID's emphasis on data provenance adds another layer of trust, ensuring that data included in researcher records is verifiable and reliable. The continuous validation of ORCID records through institutional integrations, authenticated workflows, and community oversight builds confidence in the research ecosystem as a whole. By making connections between researchers, institutions, funding bodies, and outputs more transparent and trustworthy, ORCID enhances the overall integrity of scientific research.

In sum, ORCID's infrastructure provides substantial value to the global research community by fostering a research environment that prioritises integrity, transparency, and collaboration. Its persistent identifiers and open, validated data are key enablers of knowledge discovery, research transparency, and reproducibility. This ensures that science remains interconnected and trustworthy in an increasingly complex and globalised world.

References

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